

WAYS TO INSTILL SPIRITUAL VALUES IN THE PRESCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Annotation. Today's globalization process requires the training of specialists with intellectual potential, strong knowledge. As you know, any education is built on the basis of a particular social order, and its content, goals and objectives are determined based on this order. In this sense, healthy generation education is also gaining importance in the preschool education system. The article covers the reforms carried out in this system and analyzes the practice of instilling spiritual values in the preschool education system.

Keywords: preschool education system, values, healthy generation education, globalization process, development of Science and education.

The future of each social system, the prospect of humanity, the life and standard of living of people are directly related to the development of Science and industry. The development of Science and culture depends on the extent to which educational work is carried out. This philosophical Creed is a social Law of state significance. It is known that due to the fact that knowledge and spiritual values embedded in the consciousness of a preschool child determine his future life, mutual and family relationships, caring for loved ones, the methods of national upbringing in child education and the effective use of advanced achievements of modern educators are important in the formation of a harmoniously developed child's personality.

In our opinion, the upbringing of preschool children as patriotic, humane, hardworking, spiritually mature, morally high people largely depends on the effective use in the educational system of folkloric works, which is this childhood song that was given to them in the family and preschool educational organization.

This is reflected in the "concept of continuous Spiritual Education" adopted by the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan in order to ensure the implementation of the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan PQ-4307 of May 3, 2019 on additional measures to improve the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work, as well as to educate young people as

On the topic "the child is dear, his manners are dear to him", the development and implementation of separate methodological developments for MTT educator-educators and parents using fairy tales, matals, myths, sagas, Proverbs was defined as one of the important tasks of today.

As defined in the state educational program "first step" of a preschool educational institution, the purpose of the educational process is to create appropriate conditions for the formation of competencies of General basic competencies and areas of development in children. This document reflects the overall significant 4 competencies of a child of preschool age (6-7 years old): communicative competence-the ability to use communication tools in different situations; game competence-the child's creative use of experience, knowledge and skills in the process of play and its organization, it is the basis for the educational process; social competence – behavior in communication with adults and peers in life situations, subject to ethics and norms; cognitive competence – conscious perception of the surrounding world and the use of the acquired knowledge, skills, qualifications and values for

It has been firmly concluded that preschool children occupy the rules and norms of morality in communication with adults and peers in social competence – life situations through the means of samples of folk oral creativity. The formation of high spiritual and moral qualities in children from the preschool period is a multi-stage and complex process, which requires a technological approach. Through the means of samples of folk oral creativity, it is possible to improve the system of spiritual and moral education of preschool children on the basis of interactive technologies.

The most notable aspect of interactive technology is that through it it serves to form initial etiquette skills in children, qualities of communicativity, creative thinking, leadership.

The possibility of an innovative approach to spiritual and moral education for preschool children is embodied in the educational process itself in connection with its multifactorial nature-the influence of many factors, the rapid manifestation of results, the orientation of the educator's activities (directly or indirectly), multi – stage. Multi-stage is characterized by the transition from the level of the educator's perception of one quality or another to the formation of the skill to act in accordance with the concept and, later, the acquired ones, and the formation of correct behavioral habits.

The following four stages of the technology of improving the spiritual and moral education of preschool children are indicated by the means of samples of folk oral creativity.

- Motivational stage-a process aimed at Decision-Making of interest, need and desire to listen to samples of folk oral creativity, which, taking into account the age and individual characteristics of educators, are enriched with high spiritual and moral qualities.

- The stage of content – the development of a complex of imagination, understanding and knowledge of spiritual and moral qualities that should be formed in preschool children by means of samples of folk oral creativity.

- Active stage-to involve them in practical activities by creating specific situations, forms of activity related to spiritual and moral qualities that should be formed in preschool children through the means of samples of folk oral creativity.

- A valuable stage is a process organized with the aim of transforming the spiritual and moral qualities acquired by preschool children into values, forming a strong belief in them.

Hence, from the above analyzes, shun can conclude that the main goal of the reforms carried out in the field of education is to educate young people as a harmonious generation. Raising a generation with high spirituality, deep learning, independent, thoughtful, broad worldview, spiritual trigger and healthy, morally mature qualities, for centuries, has always been considered one of the main responsible tasks in the preschool education system for teacher-educators. Preschool education is the most important and complex branch of the system of continuing education. Children at this stage manage to acquire such skills and qualifications as elementary reading and writing, calculation and acquaintance with nature, self-awareness, ability to react to reality in society at the level of perception, independent thinking. The role of spiritual values in the upbringing of a healthy generation in this process is incomparable.

References:

1. Рузиматов, Р. Я., Махкамов, Г. М., Отажонова, С. Р., & Турсунова, Ш. А. (2017). Промышленное развитие в Коканде, причины экологических проблем (1956-1975гг.). Высшая школа, (6), 77-78.
2. Isabayeva, M. M., & Otajonova, S. R. An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal.
3. Isabayeva, M. M., & Otajonova, S. R. (2021). Pedagogical factors of preparation of future teachers of biology for professional-pedagogical activities. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(6), 48-51.

4. Otajonova, S. (2021, July). PESTS OF FRUIT ORCHARDS IN THE TERRITORY OF KOKAND. In Конференции.
5. Otajonova, S. (2021). PESTS OF FRUIT ORCHARDS IN THE TERRITORY OF KOKAND: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1318>. In RESEARCH SUPPORT CENTER CONFERENCES (No. 18.06).
6. Асқарова, М. А., Отажонова, С. Р., Алимова, М. Б., & Ирматова, М. Д. (2020). READING-INTELLIGENCE AS A CAPACITY-BUILDING TOOL. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 2(7), 398-402.
7. Rakhimova, G., Narimonova, Z., Otajonova, S., & Abdulxaeva, M. (2019). Stereotypy and poetics of the endemic of recit. Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems, 11(7), 966-969.
8. Norquzieva, D. S., & Abdullaeva, N. R. (2019). PSYCHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF AGGRESSIVE BEHAVIOR IN ADOLESCENCE. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 1(6), 490-495.
9. Khamidovna, M. I., Sheralievna, N. D., & Okhunovna, M. D. (2022). CONFLICT MANAGEMENT AND TYPES OF CONFLICTS AMONG MINORS. International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education, 14(7).
10. Sheralievna, N. D. (2022). FORMATION OF CONSTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR AS A FACTOR IN THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SCHOOLCHILDREN'S EDUCATION. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(12), 1212-1216.
11. Sheralievna, N. D. (2021). DYNAMICS OF CONSTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR FORMATION IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 9(10), 666-669.
12. Sheralievna, N. D. (2022). FORMATION OF CONSTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR AS A FACTOR IN THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SCHOOLCHILDREN'S EDUCATION. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(12), 1212-1216.
13. Norqo'Ziyeva, D. S. (2021). ILK O'SPIRINLARNI KASBGA YO'NALTIRISHNING AYRIM PSIXOLOGIK MASALALARI. Scientific progress, 1(6), 1188-1192.
14. Bakhtiyarovich, U. D. (2022). IMPROVEMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF NATIONAL STRATEGIES IN THE PROCESS OF REFORMS IN THE SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL SPHERE OF THE UPDATED UZBEKISTAN. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(05), 99-102.

15. Хамрақулов, З. Й. (2022). Ҳуқуқшунослик фанларини ўқитишда замонавий таълим технологияларидан фойдаланиш. *Pedagog*, 1(3), 314-318.
16. Хамрақулов, З. Й. (2022). Ҳуқуқшунослик фанларини ўқитишда замонавий таълим технологияларидан фойдаланиш. *Pedagog*, 1(3), 314-318.
17. Khamrakulov, Z. (2022). PROBLEMS OF INCREASING LEGAL INFORMATION AND LEGAL LITERACY OF YOUTH. *Models and methods in modern science*, 1(16), 4-7.
18. Egamberdiyeva, T. U. A., & Qurbonov, J. A. (2020). Diagnostics of formation and development of intellectual culture among students. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 2(4), 512-519.
19. Akmaljonovich, K. J. (2019). The necessity of developing intellectual culture of students by the subject of philosophy. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol*, 7(12).
20. Qurbonov, J. A. (2019). Social-pedagogical content of intellectually cultural pointh. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 1(5), 437-442.
21. Akmaljonovich, K. J. (2021). The Content and Essence of the Concept of "Intellectual Culture". *European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements*, 2(5), 15-18.
22. Akmaljonovich, K. J. (2022). Role Of Philosophy Education In Forming Intellectual Culture In Future Teachers. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(11), 1366-1371.
23. Акмалжонович, Қ. Ж. (2020). ТАЛАБАЛАР ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛ МАДАНИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА ФАЛСАФА ФАНИНИ ЎҚИТИШНИНГ ПЕДАГОГИК ЖИҲАТЛАРИ. *Современное образование (Узбекистан)*, (6 (91)), 42-49.
24. Акмалжонович, Қ. Ж. (2019). Талабалар интеллектуал маданиятини ривожлантиришнинг фалсафий-педагогик жиҳатлари. *Современное образование (Узбекистан)*, (10 (83)), 3-9.
25. Akmaljonovich, K. J. (2022). Objective and Subjective Socio-Pedagogical Factors for the Formation of Intellectual Culture in Future Teachers. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(12), 148-151.
26. Юлдашева, М. М. (2017). Жамиятда ёшларнинг турли иллатлардан асрашнинг самарали йўллари. *Молодой ученый*, (4-2), 59-60.

27. Юлдашева, М. М., & Каршиева, Ш. В. (2017). Ёшларимизнинг маънавий-ғоявий шаклланишида интернетнинг роли. Молодой ученый, (4-2), 58-59.
28. Юлдашева, М. М. (2017). Мамлакатимизда ижтимоий-иқтисодий ва демократик ислохотларнинг амалга оширида миллий ғоя ва миллий тафаккурнинг ўрни. Молодой ученый, (4-2), 56-58.
29. Юлдашева, М. М., & Тобиров, О. К. (2016). РОЛЬ СМИ В ЖИЗНИ ОБЩЕСТВА. Ученый XXI века, 29.
30. Юлдашева, М. М., & Тобиров, О. К. (2016). СЕМЬЯ И ИДЕОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ДИСЦИПЛИНА ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ СИСТЕМЫ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ. Ученый XXI века, 17.
31. Юлдашева, М. М., & Аъзамов, Б. М. (2016). Бузғунчи ва вайронкор ғоялар ва уларнинг характерли хусусиятлар. Молодой ученый, (3-1), 63-64.
32. Юлдашева, М. М., & Каршиева, Ш. В. (2016). Ёшларнинг маънавий-мафкуравий хуружларнинг объектига айланиб қолиши сабаб. Молодой ученый, (3-1), 64-65.
33. Юлдашева, М. М., & Рузиматов, У. С. (2015). РОЛЬ МОЛОДЁЖИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ СИСТЕМЫ ИДЕОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ИММУНИТЕТА. Ученый XXI века, (12).
34. Urinboyev, D. (2019). Thoughts About Stratagema Of Western And Eastern Thinkers. Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University, 1(4), 147-151.
35. Bakhtiyorovich, U. D. (2022). Features of the manifestation of strategems and the relationship between them. ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(11), 96-100.
36. Bakhtiyarovich, U. D. (2022). IMPROVEMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF NATIONAL STRATEGIES IN THE PROCESS OF REFORMS IN THE SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL SPHERE OF THE UPDATED UZBEKISTAN. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(05), 99-102.
37. Baratbayev, B. B. (2021). Structural Directions Of Modern Concepts Of National Development Models Of Uzbekistan And Russia. The American Journal of Political Science Law and Criminology, 3(01), 15-20.
38. Ravshanov, F., & Baratbaev, B. (2021). Structural Directions of National Development Models of Uzbekistan and Russia. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND ANALYSIS, 4(01), 64-67.

39. Baratbaev, B. B. (2020). STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL MODELS OF DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEKISTAN AND RUSSIA. *Journal of Central Asian Social Studies*, 1(02), 21-32.
40. Баратбаев, Б. (2020). METHODS OF FORMATION OF MODELS OF NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN AND RUSSIA. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ КОНСЕНСУС*, 1(4).
41. Baratbaev, B. (2020). PROCESSES OF ORGANIZING NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE INDEPENDENT REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION. *East European Scientific Journal*, 2(11 (63)), 10-13.
42. Баратбаев, Б. (2021). Россия тараққиёт моделини амалга тадбиқ этиш сиёсати ва унинг натижалари. *Общество и инновации*, 2(1/S), 194-202.
43. Баратбаев, Б. (2021). Политика реализации модели развития России и ее результаты. *Общество и инновации*, 2(1/S), 194-202.
44. Davronovich, M. A. (2022). HUMAN PHENOMENON IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF NEW UZBEKISTAN. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW* ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(11), 40-42.
45. Davronovich, M. A. (2022). PHILOSOPHY OF THE CONCEPT OF HAPPINESS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW* ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(11), 37-39.
46. Davronovich, M. A. (2022). PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS OF RENE DEKART IN THE WORK "THE FIRST PHILOSOPHY". *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(06), 176-180.
47. Azizjon, M. (2022). COVERAGE OF ISSUES OF RAISING THE SPIRITUALITY OF A PERSON IN THE PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS OF ABU MANSUR MOTORIDI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(5), 422-428.
48. Davronovich, M. A., & Kholmirezayevich, M. I. (2020). THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND ITS SOCIO-ECONOMIC AFFECTS. *MODERN VIEWS AND RESEARCH*, 33.

